

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT: The article shares the role of information and communication technologies in teaching foreign languages. It describes the information technologies in the field of teaching foreign languages, advantages and disadvantages of using information technology.

KEY WORDS: Information technology, computerization of the educational process, self-study priority, adaptability, variability, computer training information technology is widely used in teaching English. It has been heavily studied all over the world including Uzbekistan. Considerable experience has been gained in the use of ICT, despite this, as practice shows, the extensive use of information and communication technologies in English classes in secondary schools in Uzbekistan has not yet become widespread. Support to teaching from the methodological point of view in secondary schools remains very limited and traditional which assumes that ICT opportunities are not used. One of the main reasons for this is the insufficient awareness and understanding of the concept.

INTRODUCTION. Raising awareness of methods to employ ICT creates opportunities for development of linguistic competence can radically change the learning environment. Let me start with a description of information technologies used in language teaching ICT is understood as “a set of methods and means of

collecting, storing, processing, transmitting and presenting information that expand people’s knowledge and develop their ability to manage technical and social processes” (Alexandrov, 2011). ICT may speed up the process of teaching English and contribute to a more effective organization of the lesson. The work of students in class using information technology is carried out under the guidance of a teacher, and after school hours – without this guidance. Since the independent work of students should be monitored, it should be organized on the following principles:

- Self-study priority - the information and communication environment directs students to self-study, providing the corrective function on the part of the teacher;
- Consistency and phased presentation of material based on methodological principles - the entire educational process should be carried out in accordance with methodological principles;
- Adaptability and variability - the teacher should be able to create thematic blocks containing lexical, grammatical, any other language material (Alexandrov, 2011).

Following the above principles in the independent activity of students contributes to the consolidation and improvement of their knowledge. Information technologies act as one of the main sources of information, and unlike textbooks they have a high degree of interactivity, multimedia, arouse keen interest among students and contribute to the successful development of the material.

It should also be noted that, compared with traditional educational and methodological tools, computer training programs have several advantages.

For example:

- help to plunge into a foreign language environment - participation in joint projects, forums, chats, video and web conferences;
- saturate the lessons with finished teaching materials - authentic texts, exercises aimed at developing grammatical and lexical skills, handouts;
- make it possible to create author’s curricula or materials using computer programs and Internet resources;

- offer both full-time and distance learning courses that help free up time for oral conversations and discussions;
- create favorable conditions for training, ensuring confidentiality;
- individualize the learning process - students have the opportunity to work on personal computers at a convenient pace, learning mode;
- motivate students to achieve good results.

Having listed all the advantages and advantages of information technology, it is necessary to note the disadvantages of using information technology, which must be taken into account in training. Firstly, students when searching for information on the Internet should take into account that the information provided on various sites may not be completely reliable, which can lead to incorrect formation of language and speech skills. Secondly, not being armed with web addresses can lead to the loss of a large amount of time for students, especially if this type of activity is carried out in the classroom. Thirdly, individualization of learning also has negative aspects, such as curtailing social contacts and reducing communication. Students are not interested in the successes and failures of their friends, they are completely absorbed in their worries. Overcoming these difficulties requires the teacher to verify the accuracy of the information in the suggested e-materials and the ability to skillfully facilitate the students' individual work. Thus, computer training programs can be used both in the classroom and in extracurricular time, both in group and in individual student activities. Computer technologies contribute to improving the effectiveness and motivation of learning, simulate the conditions of communicative activity, promote individualization in the conditions of teamwork, independence and activity, provide quick feedback when processing learning results, and also create a positive emotional mood.

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